

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION. THE USE OF "LABYRINTH" TECHNOLOGY IN ENTOMOLOGY LESSONS.

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Annotation

The article describes the importance of using problem situations in entomology lessons, methods and rules for creating problem situations and the use of innovative technologies in the study of insects. The importance of innovative technologies in education is described, which creates new opportunities for learning and the emergence of opportunities for personalizing learning, expanding communication opportunities and creating a more productive environment for learning entomology. It describes regular and systematic work on training, providing instant access to the necessary information and fostering important skills in working with sources, the ability to distinguish high-quality sources of information from unreliable, attracting young people to scientific activities, the formation of an innovative infrastructure of science in higher educational institutions.

Keywords: Educational objectives, spiritual and intellectual potential of society, world pedagogical experience, modern pedagogical technologies, path of independent development, positive and negative outlook on the world, advantages and disadvantages, process, methodology, innovation, creative thought, creative approach.

The future of each society is determined by the degree of development of the education system, which is its integral part and vital necessity. It is known that the continuity of education, which puts an end to excessive repetition in the system, first of all, expands the spiritual and intellectual potential of society, and, moreover, ensures the sustainable development of production as a factor in improving the social and scientific and technological progress of the state.

In the process of developing pedagogical technologies and introducing them into the educational process, as well as the rapid exchange and improvement of information technologies, each person is given the opportunity to strengthen their professional training and skills. Today, the reform and improvement of the continuing education system of our country, which is on the path of independent development, rising to a new qualitative level, introducing advanced pedagogical and information technologies into it, increasing the effectiveness of education, has risen to the level of state policy. The general pedagogical and didactic requirement for all stages of training is to increase the effectiveness of

independent work based on the student's knowledge of programming, imagination and skills, strengthen his interest in scientific thinking, pedagogical science, deepen his professional knowledge, increase their activity during theoretical and practical classes.[1,2] The world pedagogical experience confirms that the possibilities of modern pedagogical technologies to interest students in sciences, to increase their activity in independent work are limitless.

Today's task of education is to teach students to function independently in an increasing information and educational environment, to use information flows rationally. To do this, it is necessary to provide them with the opportunity and conditions for uninterrupted independent work. Interest in insects began in ancient times. Initially, they were considered as food products, but later, when animal husbandry and agriculture were displaced, they began to be studied as pests. Then it turned out that among them there are useful insects. As a result, sericulture and beekeeping emerged, which became branches of entomological science. But the scientific study of insects began in the XVII century.[1,3]

Today, entomological science and its branches face grandiose tasks-to contribute to a more complete satisfaction of the needs of the population in food, and industry in raw materials, theoretically and practically solve such important issues as protecting nature from harm, conservation and wider use of useful insect species. Innovative technologies in the study of entomology, the use of "Labyrinth" technology in entomology lessons is as follows. First of all, let's give a description of this technology. This technology is complex, multidisciplinary, aimed at studying as many problematic topics as possible. The essence of the technology is that it provides information on various branches of the subject at a time. Meanwhile, each of them is discussed from different points of view. For example, the pros and cons, Advantages and disadvantages, benefits and harms are determined. [1,4,5,6] The purpose of the technology is to form students' skills to get out of various situations and situations arising in educational and life activities, while preserving their reputation, the ability to correctly assess the situation and quickly find the right solution, to promote their competence in this area, to develop their thinking abilities and speech activity, as well as to form a culture of communication. The order of the lesson: the teacher prepares a place for the students in the form of a circle of chairs before the start of the lesson (preferably in the center of the place in the form of a circle to put a bouquet of flowers in a basket. Such arrangement of the place will help to make the training interesting and lively. If such a lesson is held outdoors, that is, in

nature, if possible, then students can even comfortably sit in a circle on the green grass.

The teacher asks students to take a place in this circle at the beginning of the lesson. Then the lesson begins with a brief conversation about the fact that the students' activities are diverse and always rich in all kinds of interesting events, events, situations. As an example, the teacher talks about one of the situations that students face or face in their activities and asks for a way out of this situation, or the teacher talks about the situation, names all three of its solutions and asks students to choose one of the three correct options and explain why they chose this option. After that, the teacher distributes the students at will into subgroups of three people, giving them the opportunity for each member of the subgroup, based on their work experience, to recall in the educational process any problematic situations that they encountered or encountered in the activities of the teacher and students, choose the most interesting, the most problematic and offer their solution (the situation, the solution of the problem). it can consist of a test of three options or an unambiguous answer) also gives the task to find.[7,8,9]

With the help of a teacher, each subgroup alternately verbally expounds to others the situations or problems they have prepared. In order to find a solution to a situation or problem that small groups are talking about, the teacher assigns them a certain time. During the allotted time, the members of the subgroup try to find a solution to the situation or problem, after the time has elapsed, the answers of the groups are listened to. For example, a situation or problem previously selected by one subgroup is recalled again, and the other subgroups, respectively, report their solutions to this situation and problem. After all the subgroups share their chosen answers, the subgroup that posed the situation or problem will express its opinion about the correct solution itself, the Teacher will also express his opinion about this situation or problem, and the entire expressed subgroup summarizes the opinions.[10,11,12]

Then the second group proceeds to discuss the situation or problem placed in the center of attention, with a discussion of all situations or problems placed in the center by groups in a similar circle. At the end of the lesson, the teacher evaluates the work of students and groups and gives recommendations on what to focus on most when looking for a solution to a situation or problem, and then ends the lesson.

This technology can also be applied in lessons, practical or laboratory classes organized during the learning process. For example, the use of this

technology in identifying problematic situations arising in the life of a student, on topics or sections mastered in an academic subject, as well as thoughts about finding solutions to problems within the topics studied in the lesson, contributes to a deeper consolidation of knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students, their correct solution when applied in practice.[13,14,15]

In the process of teaching students of this technology, new pedagogical technologies can be used in the organization of trainings, open discussions, individual, pair, small group and team work. In addition, the educational process presents samples of methods of conducting educational classes using pedagogical technologies, methods of introduction and analysis of the lesson, as well as various training sessions conducted in educational institutions.[16,17]

The methodology of the conducted educational process can be changed by each teacher depending on the content, purpose, as well as the conditions of the taught subject and subject, the capabilities and needs of students, or on the basis of the technologies presented in the learning process to create and use their own proprietary technologies.

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